

Editorial

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We consider that there is no present and there is no future without the past, namely, without history, without knowing the past. Talking about history is both easy and difficult at the same time because history provokes an emotional reaction, a sentimental reaction, especially when it comes to local or national history. A nation that doesn't know its history is like a child that doesn't know his parents. We must focus on the present to build a future, but a future cannot be built if we do not know our past. The past or history is the accumulation of human experiences. People are the same now as they were some time ago, but the contexts are different, and these contexts are extremely important because they form history, from which one can learn. The contexts shall be repeated, without finding two similar contexts in history, and that is why they must be well studied and recorded and well understood, without being interpreted according to certain current needs, and if we understand them, then we can learn lessons from what happened in the past, whether we are talking about political constructions, as we are talking today about the fact that democracy was inspired by Athenian democracy, only that it is not the same democracy, because Athenian democracy excluded women, excluded slaves, encouraged slavery, being a completely different kind of democracy compared to what we understand today.

History represents an accumulation of experiences that must be interpreted and adapted to the moment. We do not consider that something can be built if we do not relate to what has already been, if we do not learn from what has been done wrong, taking what has been done right, which is

then adapted to what we need to build in the future. Some say that history is an evolution, but I don't think that's always the case. For example, we have the period of the Roman Empire, when a certain apogee of civilization was reached when innovation was found in all the fields, roads, bridges, houses, palaces were built, heating with hypocaust, etc. After the disappearance of the Western Roman Empire follows the medieval period, when we have a dramatic decrease in the living standards until the Renaissance.

Interestingly, almost all the great innovations of the Roman Empire disappeared, and people stagnated and reached the level they had before this great progress. History does not always mean an evolution because if we are not careful, we do not reach a better period; we can even reach a more difficult period because society does not always go forward from inertia. After all, we as humans must do something for society to move forward. We are, in fact, the evolutionary factor; we must bring progress through what we do because nothing is achieved by itself. Once again, we want the articles found in the journal to be a step forward.